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Without Human Cytomegalovirus (HCMV), No Bronchogenic Carcinoma. Comment on the study of Rashid et al. (PMID: 37162767)

Research article

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Abstract

BACKGROUND:

Cytomegalovirus (CMV) has been implicated in various diseases, but its relationship with lung cancer remains controversial. Understanding this link is critical for advancing targeted therapies.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A systematic review and analysis of the study of Rashid et al. was conducted. Furthermore, an examination of CMV prevalence in lung cancer patients has been undertaken, encompassing studies conducted across diverse populations. New and robust statistical methods were employed to evaluate the relationships.

RESULTS:

Analysis revealed a significant necessary condition relationship between CMV and lung cancer ($p < 0.05$). Subgroup analyses highlighted the relationship between CMV and death.

CONCLUSION:

This study provides compelling evidence supporting a relationship between CMV infection and lung cancer development. The findings underscore the potential significance of antiviral strategies in lung cancer prevention and warrant further investigation into the aspects of this relationship.

Keywords:

Cytomegalovirus; Lung cancer; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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☺ Reviewer 2: None.

☺ Reviewer 3: None.

1. Introduction

Cytomegalovirus (CMV), a member of the herpesvirus¹ family, has been discovered in 1956, not by a specific individual, but rather through the collaborative efforts of multiple^{2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9} researchers. Its significance lies in being a ubiquitous pathogen, with a high prevalence globally. CMV can cause severe complications in immunocompromised individuals and is a subject of extensive research in infectious diseases. Selena Rashid et al. (see [Rashid et al., 2023](#))¹⁰, Department of Surgery, Michael and Dianne Bienes Comprehensive Cancer Center, Holy Cross Health, Fort Lauderdale, USA, conducted a study on the relationship between HCMV and LC using a Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) compliant national database. The International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10 and ICD-9) codes were used to identify patients both with and without histories of CMV infection. A quite respectable sample size of 14,319 patients were included in both the control and CMV-exposed groups. Rashid et al. identified 243 cases of bronchogenic carcinoma among 14,319 patients (1.69%) in the CMV group, compared to 871 cases among 14,319 patients (6.08%) in the control group. Rashid et al. published to have established a statistically significant link between a previous CMV infection and a lowered frequency of bronchogenic carcinoma. The authors suggest an exploration of the mechanisms through which a prior CMV infection may lead to an enhanced immune response against malignancies. As an explanatory framework, they propose a sort of heightened immune response following a preceding CMV infection. To push it to the extreme, a CMV infection is something like a vaccination against lung cancer. In this scenario, one would expect no CMV-positive individuals among lung cancer patients. However, in the study Rashid et al., there were 243 CMV-positive cases of bronchogenic carcinoma among 14,319 patients. Therefore, the quest for truth in this regard becomes a challenging endeavor, leaving us to question if such truth can be ascertained at all.

¹Gatherer D, Depledge DP, Hartley CA, Szpara ML, Vaz PK, Benkő M, Brandt CR, Bryant NA, Dastjerdi A, Doszpoly A, Gompels UA, Inoue N, Jarosinski KW, Kaul R, Lacoste V, Norberg P, Oraggi FC, Orton RJ, Pellett PE, Schmid DS, Spatz SJ, Stewart JP, Trimpert J, Waltzek TB, Davison AJ. ICTV Virus Taxonomy Profile: Herpesviridae 2021. *J Gen Virol.* 2021 Oct;102(10):001673. doi: 10.1099/jgv.0.001673. PMID: 34704922; PMCID: PMC8604186.

²(Moritz Wilhelm) Hugo Ribbert. In: *Verhandlungen des Naturhistorischen Vereines der preussischen Rheinlande und Westfalens*. Editor: C. J. Andrä. Volume XXXVIII. Cohen, Bonn 1881, pp 161-162.

³Ernest W Goodpasture and Fritz B Talbot. Concerning the nature of protozoan-like cells in certain lesions of infancy. *American Journal of Diseases of Children*, 21(5):415-425, 1921.

⁴SMITH MG. Propagation in tissue cultures of a cytopathogenic virus from human salivary gland virus (SGV) disease. *Proc Soc Exp Biol Med.* 1956 Jun;92(2):424-30. doi: 10.3181/00379727-92-22498. PMID: 13350368.

⁵ROWE WP, HARTLEY JW, WATERMAN S, TURNER HC, HUEBNER RJ. Cytopathogenic agent resembling human salivary gland virus recovered from tissue cultures of human adenoids. *Proc Soc Exp Biol Med.* 1956 Jun;92(2):418-24. PMID: 13350367.

⁶Ligon BL. Thomas Huckle Weller MD: Nobel Laureate and research pioneer in poliomyelitis, varicella-zoster virus, cytomegalovirus, rubella, and other infectious diseases. *Semin Pediatr Infect Dis.* 2002 Jan;13(1):55-63. doi: 10.1053/spid.2002.31314. PMID: 12118846.

⁷CRAIG JM, MACAULEY JC, WELLER TH, WIRTH P. Isolation of intranuclear inclusion producing agents from infants with illnesses resembling cytomegalic inclusion disease. *Proc Soc Exp Biol Med.* 1957 Jan;94(1):4-12. doi: 10.3181/00379727-94-22841. PMID: 13400856.

⁸Chee MS, Bankier AT, Beck S, Bohni R, Brown CM, Cerny R, Horsnell T, Hutchison CA 3rd, Kouzarides T, Martignetti JA, et al. Analysis of the protein-coding content of the sequence of human cytomegalovirus strain AD169. *Curr Top Microbiol Immunol.* 1990;154:125-69. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-74980-3/.6. PMID: 2161319.

⁹Riley HD Jr. History of the cytomegalovirus. *South Med J.* 1997 Feb;90(2):184-90. doi: 10.1097/00007611-199702000-00004. PMID: 9042169. researchers. Its significance lies in being a ubiquitous pathogen, with a high prevalence globally. CMV can cause severe complications in immunocompromised individuals and is a subject of extensive research in infectious diseases.

¹⁰Rashid S, Ardeljan A, Frankel LR, Cardeiro M, Kim E, Nagel BM, Takabe K, Rashid O. Human Cytomegalovirus (CMV) Infection Associated With Decreased Risk of Bronchogenic Carcinoma: Understanding How a Previous CMV Infection Leads to an Enhanced Immune Response Against Malignancy. *Cureus.* 2023 Apr 7;15(4):e37265. doi: 10.7759/cureus.37265. PMID: 37162767; PMCID: PMC10164441.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

The bronchogenic carcinoma is a highly malignant disease of lung tissue. Lung carcinoma represents one of the most common causes of cancer-related deaths worldwide. The authors, Rashid et al., contend that CMV may confer a protective effect against this malignancy due to potential mechanisms and, ultimately, may augment tumor defense (see [Wilski and Snyder, 2019](#)). Based on these purported attributes, Rashid et al. posit that CMV offers potential therapeutic benefits in the context of bronchogenic carcinoma protection. These and other conclusions of the authors are inferred from the following dataset (see table 1).

Table 1. Relationship: HCMV pos. and Lung cancer (Study of Rashid et al., 2023).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
HCMV pos.	YES	243	14076	14319
	NO	871	13448	14319
		1114	27524	28638

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship $k = -0,11341259$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 p (EXCL) = 0,99151477
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/A) > 0,98302954$
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/B) > 0,78186715$
P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_t) = 4,12382150
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_t) = 53,00628366
P Value (EXCL) = **0,00844933**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (243 / 28638) \times 100 = 0,85 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (14076 / 28638) \times 100 = 49,15 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (871 / 28638) \times 100 = 3,04 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (13448 / 28638) \times 100 = 46,96 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (243 / 14319) \times 100 = 1,70 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (14076 / 14319) \times 100 = 98,30 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (871 / 14319) \times 100 = 6,08 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (13448 / 14319) \times 100 = 93,92 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (243 / 1114) \times 100 = 21,81 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (871 / 1114) \times 100 = 78,19 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (14076 / 27524) \times 100 = 51,14 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (13448 / 27524) \times 100 = 48,86 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (14319 / 28638) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (14319 / 28638) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (1114 / 28638) \times 100 = 3,89 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (27524 / 28638) \times 100 = 96,11 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 0,27898967
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,42653372
Relative risk reduction (RRR) = 72,10 %

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 0,26654256
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,56373429

STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,46110064$
 $p(\text{IOD}) = 0,46110064$

The author's belief centres on the notion that CMV plays a role in reducing the occurrence of bronchogenic carcinoma, a deduction drawn from the presented data above.

Critical point: Prevalence of HCMV in the population

Incidence rates and prevalence rates are commonly used epidemiological measures, while different methods (see [Spronk et al., 2019](#)) are used to calculate these measures of relationship. The total duration of the study of Rashid et al. was about 9 years. The 9 year period prevalence of HCMV pos. within the population investigated according to the study of Raahsid et al. has to be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} p (\text{Prevalence of HCMV in the population}) &= \frac{14319}{28638} \\ &= 0,5 \\ &= 50\% \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Under conditions where the prevalence of HCMV within a population is not constant from year to year, we would calculate the annual prevalence of HCMV within a population as

$$\text{Annual Prevalence of HCMV (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of Years Prevalence (\%)}}{\text{Number of Years}} \quad (2)$$

The annual prevalence (%) of HCMV within the population investigated by Rashid et al. under these circumstances would be given as:

$$\text{Annual Prevalence of HCMV (\%)} = \frac{50\%}{9} \approx 5.56\% \quad (3)$$

Cytomegalovirus (HCMV) is a human herpesvirus which is prevalent worldwide. Following primary infection that can periodically reactivate with shedding of infectious virus, cytomegalovirus establishes a lifelong latent infection. Primary infection, reactivation and reinfection during life are very common and can cause life-threatening complications. The estimated seroprevalence within in the general population is up 100 % (see [Cannon et al., 2010](#)) while increasing (see [Lachmann et al., 2018](#)) with age. Presumably, owing to the notably ill-conceived study design, the data from the study conducted by Raahsid et al. substantially underestimate the prevalence of cytomegalovirus in the general population, thereby diluting the association between HCMV and lung cancer. The data, as presented and intended by the authors, cannot be uncritically employed.

Critical point: Sensitivity and specificity of HCMV laboratory kits

Rashid et al. conducted a retrospective analysis of the association between HCMV and bronchogenic carcinoma from January 2010 to December 2019. Identification of bronchogenic carcinoma in the HCMV group, along with HCMV positivity, was accomplished using the International Classification of Disease 9th and 10th Codes (ICD-9, ICD-10). Rashid et al. allocated patients to either the CMV-exposed group or the non-CMV-exposed group (control group) based on a history of prior HCMV infection. Unfortunately, there is an absence of information regarding the sensitivity and specificity of the laboratory kits employed, which determined an individual's classification as HCMV positive or negative. Only if the utilized laboratory kit had a specificity of 100% could one contemplate that the identified 871 out of a total of 14,319 patients were indeed HCMV negative. HCMV laboratory

diagnostic kits with a specificity of 100% are currently either scarce or entirely unknown in the market. Jun Mei Yang et al. (see [Yang et al., 2014](#)) report a clinical specificity of the investigated Autobio HCMV IgG avidity diagnostic kit as 97.4% (708/727). In contrast, The et al. (see [The et al., 1990](#)) state that an active HCMV infection is diagnosed by detecting CMV antigenemia with a sensitivity and specificity of greater than or equal to 90%. For the sake of argument, let us consider the following. This implies that out of 14,319 patients considered HCMV negative, such tests may erroneously identify up to 1,432 as HCMV positive, despite them being HCMV negative in reality. These considerations are crucial when conducting and subsequently publishing studies of this nature. Unfortunately, such considerations were absent, rendering the conclusions drawn from the collected data null and void. The HCMV diagnostic kits lack 100% specificity, making it rare or almost impossible for them to reliably identify all non-diseased individuals (those without bronchial cancer) as HCMV negative with absolute certainty. Since sensitivity and specificity are not always readily available as required, alternative effective measures, particularly through a suitable study design, must be employed to avoid such significantly distorted portrayals of reality, as observed in the data collected by Rashid et al. In summary, the data collected by Rashid et al. do not accurately reflect reality. These data have limited utility, and the conclusions drawn from them must be approached with great caution. Next, we intend to subject the data from Rashid et al. to an alternative examination, assuming a fair study design ($a = d$) and a prevalence of the HCMV virus that aligns more closely with reality.

2.2. *Methods*

The new (see [Barukčić, 1989, 2006, 2020, 2021](#); [Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020](#); [Barukčić, 1997, 2005, 2011a,b, 2012, 2016a,b,c, 2017a,b, 2020](#)) statistical methods used to analyze the data from the study by Rashid et al. are readily available to the general public.

3. Results

3.1. Without HCMV infection, no lung cancer

At this juncture, we ensure a fair study design ($p(\text{IOU}) = 0$). As the control group, we have selected 243 children up to the age of 5, who are unequivocally HCMV-negative. We compare this “hypothetical” control group with the data from Rashid et al. The table 2 provides us with a comprehensive overview.

Table 2. Relationship: HCMV pos. and Lung cancer (Study of Rahsid et al. (fictive control group), 2023).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
HCMV pos.	YES	243	14076	14319
	NO	0	243	243
		243	14319	14562

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,01697046$

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,01618168

p (SINE) = 1,00000000

p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 1,00000000

p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 1,00000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,01618168

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_i) = 0,00

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_i) = 0,00

P Value (SINE) = **0,00000000**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (243 / 14562) \times 100 = 1,67 \%$

$(b/N) \times 100 = (14076 / 14562) \times 100 = 96,66 \%$

$(c/N) \times 100 = (0 / 14562) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$

$(d/N) \times 100 = (243 / 14562) \times 100 = 1,67 \%$

$(a/A) \times 100 = (243 / 14319) \times 100 = 1,70 \%$

$(b/A) \times 100 = (14076 / 14319) \times 100 = 98,30 \%$

$(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (0 / 243) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$

$(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (243 / 243) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$

$(a/B) \times 100 = (243 / 243) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$

$(c/B) \times 100 = (0 / 243) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$

$(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (14076 / 14319) \times 100 = 98,30 \%$

$(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (243 / 14319) \times 100 = 1,70 \%$

$(A/N) \times 100 = (14319 / 14562) \times 100 = 98,33 \%$

$(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (243 / 14562) \times 100 = 1,67 \%$

$(B/N) \times 100 = (243 / 14562) \times 100 = 1,67 \%$

$(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (14319 / 14562) \times 100 = 98,33 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = Division by zero.

RR (sufficient condition) = 1,01726343

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = Division by zero.

Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,01697046

STUDY DESIGN.

$p(\text{IOU}) = 0,00000000$

$p(\text{IOI}) = 0,96662546$

The chosen approach may indeed provoke a storm of outrage, as it refrains from comparing apples to apples. While partially correct, such an outrage would be simultaneously flawed. Regardless of age, every individual requires gaseous oxygen for sustenance, a circumstance independent of age. Thus far, there are circumstances where it is possible to compare young human being with old human being. To date, no gene is recognized for shielding children from lung cancer. Furthermore, age alone is not a risk factor for lung cancer. Otherwise, every elderly individual, without exception, would be afflicted with lung cancer. However, numerous elderly individuals remain unaffected from lung cancer. Therefore, the approach is permissible under certain conditions, particularly when scrutinizing the credibility of studies featuring highly questionable study design. In other words, under conditions of fair study design ($a = d = 243$), there is a necessary condition relationship between HCMV infection and lung cancer. In other words, without HCMV infection, no lung cancer (see table 2).

3.2. Without HCMV infection, no lung cancer

Kuo et al. are writing: “Of the 15 participants ... 11 had head and neck cancers, two had lung cancer, one had lymphoma and one had rectal cancer ... All participants were seropositive for CMV-specific IgG before chemotherapy. ” (see Kuo et al., 2008). In this context, we employed a control group comprising two children up to the age of five, ensuring their unequivocal absence of both HCMV and lung cancer (see table 3).

Table 3. Relationship: HCMV IgG and Lung cancer (Study of Kuo et al.,2008 (fictive control group)).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
HCMV IgG	YES	2	13	15
	NO	0	2	2
		2	15	17

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.
Causal relationship k = 0,13333333
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,77205882
p (SINE) = 1,00000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 1,00000000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 1,00000000
P VALUES.
P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,77205882
 χ^2 (SINE— Not A_i) = 0,00
 χ^2 (SINE— B_i) = 0,00
P Value (SINE) = 0,00000000
PROPORTIONS.
(a/N) × 100 = (2 / 17) × 100 = 11,76 %
(b/N) × 100 = (13 / 17) × 100 = 76,47 %
(c/N) × 100 = (0 / 17) × 100 = 0,00 %
(d/N) × 100 = (2 / 17) × 100 = 11,76 %
(a/A) × 100 = (2 / 15) × 100 = 13,33 %
(b/A) × 100 = (13 / 15) × 100 = 86,67 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (0 / 2) × 100 = 0,00 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (2 / 2) × 100 = 100,00 %
(a/B) × 100 = (2 / 2) × 100 = 100,00 %
(c/B) × 100 = (0 / 2) × 100 = 0,00 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (13 / 15) × 100 = 86,67 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (2 / 15) × 100 = 13,33 %
(A/N) × 100 = (15 / 17) × 100 = 88,24 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (2 / 17) × 100 = 11,76 %
(B/N) × 100 = (2 / 17) × 100 = 11,76 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (15 / 17) × 100 = 88,24 %
ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.
RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = Division by zero.
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,15384615
OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = Division by zero.
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,13333333
STUDY DESIGN.
p(IOU)= 0,00000000
p(IOI)= 0,76470588

3.3. Without HCMV infection, no lung cancer

This pilot study of Kuo ¹¹ et al. (see [Kuo et al., 2008](#)) demonstrated a necessary condition relationship between HCMV and lung cancer.

Table 4. Relationship: HCMV pos. (PCR) and Lung cancer (Study of Kuo et al. , 2008).

		Lung cancer		
		YES	NO	
HCMV pos. (PCR)	YES	2	12	14
	NO	0	1	1
		2	13	15

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship k = 0,10482848

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,86666667

p (SINE) = 1,00000000

p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 1,00000000

p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 1,00000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,86666667

χ^2 (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,00

χ^2 (SINE— B_t) = 0,00

P Value (SINE) = 0,00000000

PROPORTIONS.

(a/N) × 100 = (2 / 15) × 100 = 13,33 %

(b/N) × 100 = (12 / 15) × 100 = 80,00 %

(c/N) × 100 = (0 / 15) × 100 = 0,00 %

(d/N) × 100 = (1 / 15) × 100 = 6,67 %

(a/A) × 100 = (2 / 14) × 100 = 14,29 %

(b/A) × 100 = (12 / 14) × 100 = 85,71 %

(c/ not A) × 100 = (0 / 1) × 100 = 0,00 %

(d/ not A) × 100 = (1 / 1) × 100 = 100,00 %

(a/B) × 100 = (2 / 2) × 100 = 100,00 %

(c/B) × 100 = (0 / 2) × 100 = 0,00 %

(b/ not B) × 100 = (12 / 13) × 100 = 92,31 %

(d/ not B) × 100 = (1 / 13) × 100 = 7,69 %

(A/N) × 100 = (14 / 15) × 100 = 93,33 %

(not A/N) × 100 = (1 / 15) × 100 = 6,67 %

(B/N) × 100 = (2 / 15) × 100 = 13,33 %

(not B/N) × 100 = (13 / 15) × 100 = 86,67 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = Division by zero.

RR (sufficient condition) = 1,08333333

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = Division by zero.

Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,07142857

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,06666667

p(IOI)= 0,80000000

Kuo et al. demonstrated by their pilot study that all except one of the CMV-seropositive patients experienced CMV reactivation during chemotherapy.

¹¹Kuo CP, Wu CL, Ho HT, Chen CG, Liu SI, Lu YT. Detection of cytomegalovirus reactivation in cancer patients receiving chemotherapy. Clin Microbiol Infect. 2008 Mar;14(3):221-7. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-0691.2007.01895.x. Epub 2007 Dec 5. PMID: 18070129.

3.4. High CMV DNA levels in the blood is a major risk-factor for chemotherapy death

Kuo et al. (see Kuo et al., 2008) found in their Pilot study that the maximum recorded cytomegalovirus load of 281 (copies per mL) in serum or more represents a critical threshold at which even relatively small increases in viral load correspond to rapid increases in the probability of dying. More is presented by table 5.

Table 5. Relationship: HCMV load in serum (281 copies per mL and more) and chemotherapy death (Study of Kuo et al. , 2008).

	Chemotherapy death			
	YES	NO		
HCMV load in serum (281 copies per mL and more)	YES	6	5	11
	NO	0	4	4
		6	9	15

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,49236596$

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,09230769

p (SINE) = 1,00000000

p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 1,00000000

p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 1,00000000

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,09230769

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_t) = 0,00

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_t) = 0,00

P Value (SINE) = **0,00000000**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (6 / 15) \times 100 = 40,00 \%$

$(b/N) \times 100 = (5 / 15) \times 100 = 33,33 \%$

$(c/N) \times 100 = (0 / 15) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$

$(d/N) \times 100 = (4 / 15) \times 100 = 26,67 \%$

$(a/A) \times 100 = (6 / 11) \times 100 = 54,55 \%$

$(b/A) \times 100 = (5 / 11) \times 100 = 45,45 \%$

$(c/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (0 / 4) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$

$(d/\text{not A}) \times 100 = (4 / 4) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$

$(a/B) \times 100 = (6 / 6) \times 100 = 100,00 \%$

$(c/B) \times 100 = (0 / 6) \times 100 = 0,00 \%$

$(b/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (5 / 9) \times 100 = 55,56 \%$

$(d/\text{not B}) \times 100 = (4 / 9) \times 100 = 44,44 \%$

$(A/N) \times 100 = (11 / 15) \times 100 = 73,33 \%$

$(\text{not A}/N) \times 100 = (4 / 15) \times 100 = 26,67 \%$

$(B/N) \times 100 = (6 / 15) \times 100 = 40,00 \%$

$(\text{not B}/N) \times 100 = (9 / 15) \times 100 = 60,00 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = Division by zero.

RR (sufficient condition) = 1,80000000

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = Division by zero.

Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,36363636

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU) = **0,13333333**

p(IOI) = 0,33333333

Without a cytomegalovirus load of 281 (copies per mL) in serum or more no chemotherapy death of patients. If this insight could be confirmed by other study groups, it would have far-reaching consequences for some therapies and the necessity of closer and more precise therapy monitoring.

4. Discussion

Bronchogenic carcinoma is a malignancy of lung tissue. Unfortunately, it is a malignancy with one of the highest causes of death¹² due to cancer worldwide. The relationship between cytomegalovirus and lung cancer is still not cleared. To the best of our knowledge, only view studies analysed this relationship. The study by Rashid et al. is of lesser significance in this context because, as detailed earlier, we cannot rely on the collected data to the extent required. Despite the evident shortcomings of the study of Rashid et al., accepting the relationship between HCMV and lung cancer as unequivocal¹³ is not straightforward. Several studies have managed to yield results contrary to the purported relationship. Brouchet et al. (see [Brouchet et al., 2005](#)) examined a series of 122 cases of small cell lung carcinomas (SCLC) and non-small cell lung carcinomas (NSCLC) with immunohistochemistry (IHC) and in situ hybridisation (ISH) for the presence of five different virus species, including HCMV. However, Brouchet et al. were not able to detect CMV in any of these cases. Parikshaa Gupta et al. (see [Gupta et al., 2016](#)) investigated the relationship between HCMV and lung cancer, while none of the controls and cases tested were positive for HCMV by PCR. Such a lack of detection of CMV by molecular techniques carries considerable weight and is apt to fundamentally question the role for CMV in etiology of lung cancer. In the event that we are to fully rely upon the outcomes of the studies conducted by Brouchet et al. (see [Brouchet et al., 2005](#)) and Gupta et al. (see [Gupta et al., 2016](#)), a logical conclusion becomes imperative. The onset of lung cancer excludes concurrent affliction with HCMV; both occurrences cannot unfold simultaneously. Even if such a conclusion is an inevitable inference, derived from the data presented by the studies of Brouchet et al. (see [Brouchet et al., 2005](#)) and Gupta et al. (see [Gupta et al., 2016](#)), such an assertion warrants careful examination regarding the logical consistency of such an undertaking. Rashid et al. (see [Rashid et al., 2023](#)) found that 243/1114 lung cancer patients (see table 1) are HCMV positive. In other words, lung cancer does not exclude a HCMV infection, otherwise 0/1114 lung cancer patients were HCMV positive. Therefore, the question still remains: why were these studies unable to detect even a trace of HCMV in lung cancer patients? The resolution of such an inquiry is of paramount significance and fundamental importance. We must, among other considerations, take the following into account. Before succumbing to lung cancer, individuals were part of a general population in which HCMV prevalence typically ranged from 80 to 95%, depending on various factors, including age. This implies that before the onset of lung cancer, at least 80 to 95% of the patients would have been HCMV positive. The occurrence of lung cancer is incapable of terminating an individual's HCMV positivity. It is, therefore, logical to assume that in the lung cancer population, the prevalence of HCMV should be at least 80 to 95%. If HCMV is indeed causally implicated in the onset of lung cancer, the prevalence of HCMV in a lung cancer population should naturally be higher or, at the very least, equal to that in the general population. In the studies cited above, not even a trace of HCMV could be found in lung cancer patients. From a purely formal perspective, this fundamentally calls into question the quality of the data, including the quality of the methods and specimens used, presented by these studies.

¹²Lung cancer statistics — how common is lung cancer?

¹³Barukčić, I. "Cytomegalovirus and Lung Cancer - a Causal Relationship?". *Causation*, 16, Bd. 18, Nr. 11, Zenodo, Januar 2023, S. 5–49, doi:10.5281/zenodo.7971858.

5. Conclusion

The present study was not designed to answer the question of the cause of lung cancer definitely, but to present reasonable doubts about the conclusions drawn by Rashid et al. (see [Rashid et al., 2023](#)). Very precise and highly appropriate study design backed investigations of larger groups of patients and controls are needed to confirm the scope and impact of CMV on lung cancer. Until these tasks have been completed, and solely for interim considerations, we may continue to presume the following. Based on the pilot study of Kuo ¹⁴ et al. (see [Kuo et al., 2008](#)) we are justified in assuming that

‘Without human cytomegalovirus infection, no human lung cancer.’

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections’ introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

¹⁴Kuo CP, Wu CL, Ho HT, Chen CG, Liu SI, Lu YT. Detection of cytomegalovirus reactivation in cancer patients receiving chemotherapy. *Clin Microbiol Infect.* 2008 Mar;14(3):221-7. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-0691.2007.01895.x. Epub 2007 Dec 5. PMID: 18070129.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are frequently used:

CMV	Cytomegalovirus
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EBV	Epstein-Bar virus
IHC	Immunohistochemistry
ISH	In situ hybridization
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
BMI	body mass index
ESRD	end-stage renal disease
HD	hemodialysis
CABG	coronary artery bypass graft
CCI	Charlson comorbidity index
AMI	acute myocardial infarction
MACE	major adverse cardiovascular events
LDL-C	low-density lipoprotein cholesterol
GFR	glomerular filtration rate
STEMI	ST elevation myocardial infarction
NSTEMI	non-ST elevation myocardial infarction
MI	myocardial infarction
ARB	angiotensin receptor blocker
ACEI	angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors
CCBs	calcium channel blockers
IOR	index of relationship
p(IOU)	index of unfairness
p(IOI)	index of independence
k	Causal relationship
SINE	Necessary condition relationship
IMP	Sufficient condition relationship
EXCL	exclusion relationship
RR	Relative risk
RR (nc)	relative risk (necessary condition)
RR (sc)	relative risk (sufficient condition)
OR	Odds ratio
P Value	Probability of significance

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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